

D7.1 PHAntastic website & logo

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Deliverable Information Sheet

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¹¹ **Type** [1] R=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other_
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V	Date	Comments	Authors
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VF	31/10/2024	Final version, approved by the project coordinator and submitted to EC.	Carmen Fernández (CETEC)

Document verification and approval

	Name	Organisation	Date	Visa
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PHAntastic Manager	Dorottya Kalo	RVL	31/10/2024	OK
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Keywords list

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1. Executive summary

The project website and visual identity are two core components of the PHAntastic project and are the second deliverable as part of WP7.

This document, due in M2, outlines the respective elements of the PHAntastic landing page and presents the logo which serves as the basis for the visual identity of the project.

1.1. Project Overview

The PHAntastic project uses polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) to develop biodegradable mulch film and growth foam delivery systems, reducing the need for synthetic agrochemical inputs and non-biodegradable polymers. The two families of PHA-based delivery systems containing active bioproducts are demonstrated in European horticultural and tree nursery settings (TRL 6). The project will contribute to the elimination of 23,000 tons of agrochemicals and 680 tons of microplastics by 2050.

Coordinated by CETEC, this €7.4M Horizon Europe initiative (2024–2028) supports sustainable agriculture and aligns with EU targets for reduced environmental impact and enhanced food security.

2. Website

2.1. Introduction

The project website is the main communication and dissemination platform for the PHAntastic project and will house all project information, ongoing activities, deliverables, and key results. It will also connect the target stakeholders to additional PHAntastic resources including the newsletter and social media channels.

Though this deliverable is submitted in M2, the website will be continuously updated throughout the project duration and new sections could be added as needed to highlight the work and results in an effective and user-friendly manner.

2.2. Website Objectives

The project website will be a public platform for visitors to see, learn about and visualise the added value of project materials and learn about PHAntastic results and impacts via videos, infographics, factsheets, interviews and other available communication materials. As the primary communication and dissemination platform, the website allows stakeholders, policymakers, and the media access to the project development and results, and to see the added value of the use of biodegradable polymers in horticultural and tree nursery settings.

In addition, the project's social media channels will lead back to the website for more traffic, with all public deliverables integrated on the website and promoted through the project's communication channels. The key aim of the website is to:

- Provide an online platform and communication tools for effective dissemination of the project's main activities, findings, processes and progress on results.

Delivered in M2, the PHAntastic landing page is hosted at <https://phantastic-project.eu/> and in the upcoming months, it will be updated as the project progresses by REVOLVE and the project partners.

Throughout late 2024 and early 2025, as content is developed and approved by the consortium, REVOLVE will create and include new pages, including press releases, event details, articles, partner profiles, work package updates, and additional features (for a timeline, see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Timeline outlining the stages of the PHAntastic website development

2.3. Content

2.3.1. Landing page

Figure 2 PHAntastic landing page. Part 1

The aim of the landing page is to present an engaging and concise introduction to the project, while aligning with EU funding visibility and communication standards.

The objectives of the PHAntastic landing page are to:

- 1. Present the purpose of the project:** The tagline serves as a clear, memorable phrase that summarizes the project's goal or impact.
- 2. Briefly outline the mission:** The golden paragraph is at focus, offering a summary that explains the project's importance, scope, and key objectives for a non-technical audience.
- 3. Showcase Partnerships and Collaborative Reach:** Displaying all partners' logos highlights the collaboration that will take place throughout the project, builds credibility, and signals the expertise of the consortium.
- 4. Possibility to receive news on the project:** A link to the project's LinkedIn page has been added to the landing page as well as a newsletter sign-up form, which is linked to Mailchimp, and which allows visitors to receive regular updates on the project.
- 5. Fulfil EU Visibility Requirements:** The landing page is visually aligned with EU branding guidelines, particularly regarding logos, layout, and acknowledgment of funding, ensuring transparency and uniformity across EU-funded projects.

Figure 3 PHAntastic landing page. Part 2

The page includes:

- Tagline, golden paragraph
- Access to the project's LinkedIn page & sign-up link to the PHAntastic newsletter

- List of consortium partners and their corresponding logos with hyperlinks to the website
- EU funding disclaimer

2.3.2. Homepage

The homepage will be an all-in-one hub linking all pages of the website, facilitating easy navigation, drive traffic back to the project's social media channels as well as to encourage subscriptions to the newsletter. It will present all the key information of the project which will be aligned with the project's visual identity (see Annex – Visual Identity Guidelines)

Below all the essential elements are listed that will be an integral part of this page:

- Project logo, image, project graphics, tagline, social media icons and navigation menu
- Golden paragraph and objectives
- Upcoming events
- Press coverage
- Newsletter subscription link
- The EU emblem and disclaimer
- Privacy and data policy
- Contacts of project coordinator and communications manager

2.3.3. About page

This page will include more detailed information on the project activities, such as work packages, as well as present the consortium more in-depth. This page will include:

- Project description
- Objectives
- Members of the consortium
- Project resource links

2.3.4. What's on?

2.3.4.1. Events

This page will promote upcoming event related projects, integrating project-specific agendas, links to registrations into the corresponding events websites as well as serve as a repository for past events that are relevant to the subject matter. There will be two categories to distinguish between 1) events hosted by the project and 2) external events.

2.3.4.2. News

Latest updates, articles, and announcements on the project's progress and related topics of interest. This section will keep visitors informed about recent developments and achievements within the consortium and its extended network. A 'block' set up will make the page easily customisable and can help in distinguishing between press coverage and press releases as well as additional articles relevant to the project.

2.3.4.3. Newsletter

This page will host all past newsletters as well a newsletter sign-up which will be integrated via banners and clickable links. This will activate a pop-up form to be filled in by the user.

2.3.5. Resources

A repository of public **project deliverables** and publications, audiovisual materials, additional resources such as factsheets, image bank, videos and visual identity kit and published newsletters. This section will offer insights into the resources generated throughout the project's duration.

2.3.6. Footer

The footer of the website will appear on all pages and includes:

- Project logo
- The EU emblem and disclaimer
- Contact details for project coordinator and communication coordinator
- An expanded navigation menu
- Links to social media channels.
- Link to the privacy policy

2.3.7. GDPR

The website is GDPR-compliant, and all visitors and newsletter subscribers can easily access the privacy policy and terms of use. The website will be continuously updated throughout the project duration and is monitored via Google Analytics.

3. Logo

The visual identity of the project will differentiate PHAntastic from other projects working on advances biobased materials for sustainable agriculture. It comprises the logo, icon, and slogan. The logo will be the visual messenger of the project and will be reflected in all the communication materials:

Figure 4 PHAntastic logo

The icon of the PHAntastic includes a cycloalkane, together with the PHAntastic wordmark. The cycloalkane represents the projects relevance to the use of biopolymers.

The slogan (also known as the tagline) is an actionable statement representing the goal of the project:

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

An icon was created which can be used when there is a lack of space, or it is more optimal to represent the project:

Figure 5 PHAntastic icon

The icon is utilised on social media platforms as account profile photos and other communication materials as needed. A comprehensive guide on the correct usage of the logo, tagline, and the project colour scheme can be found the **Error!** **Reference source not found..**

Annex – Visual Identity Guidelines

Not yet approved by the EC.

Visual Identity Guidelines

NOVEMBER 2024

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Introduction

The PHAntastic visual identity plays an essential role in promoting the project; as such, it is imperative to respect these guidelines when using the logo, font and colours for any external or internal communication, such as presentation templates, posters, business cards, flyers, social media, and so on.

The following guidelines provide a framework for using the brand identity in a consistent manner. Consistency communicates reliability and provides the foundation for working together in an efficient way. While maintaining the highest quality standard, our choice of words and images are opportunities to show that we understand and engage with our audiences.

These visual identity guidelines are a living document and may be updated to accommodate changing requirements. If you require assistance, additional support materials, or adjustments for a specific situation, please contact the PHAntastic team. Likewise, if for any reason, you need to work outside the scope of these visual identity guidelines, please contact the Communication leads.

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The logo

About the logo and its meaning

Rationale

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams.

The logo prominently features the letters "PHA" in the wordmark, designed to echo the hexagonal structures commonly found in chemical representations. This design choice serves to emphasize the project's core focus on PHA polymers and their potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

The color palette selected for the project features vibrant and engaging hues, intentionally chosen to evoke a sense of innovation, optimism, and progress. It also includes some more muted dark green and brown hues for a more natural and earthy look.

The color palette includes vibrant hues, evoking a sense of innovation and progress. The chosen typeface, Dita, is a rounded sans serif that blends the freshness of display type with the discipline of a text face, giving the branding a contemporary and approachable feel.

The logo

Logo colour variations

Fullcolour

This is the default version of the logo, to be used on white or light backgrounds.

Dark purple + White

For use on lighter coloured backgrounds and photographs. Be careful that the logo needs to stand out against the background.

Purple + White

For use on darker coloured backgrounds and photographs. Be careful that the logo needs to stand out against the background.

Dark purple

For use on monochrome layouts or documents, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

Purple

For use on monochrome layouts or documents, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

Black

For use on black and white layouts or documents, on dark backgrounds, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

White

For use on monochrome layouts or documents, on dark backgrounds, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

The logo

Minimum size and safe area

Minimum sizes

The minimum size is indicated by the width of the logo. The logo should never be smaller than the minimum indicated sizes to avoid compromising its visibility.

The width of the inline logo should never be smaller than 25 mm in print or 70 px in digital media.

Safe area

Keep all other graphic elements, logos or margins at a minimum distance as defined by the “Safe area” line. The minimum safe area is equal to the cap-height of the logo text.

Colours

The project has an extended colour palette to meet all communication needs

Dark purple
CMYK: 94 / 93 / 29 / 18
RGB: 52 / 48 / 104
HEX: #343068

Purple
CMYK: 56 / 70 / 0 / 0
RGB: 134 / 97 / 193
HEX: #8661C1

Light purple
CMYK: 17 / 35 / 0 / 0
RGB: 206 / 170 / 214
HEX: #CEAAD6

Brown
CMYK: 47 / 64 / 64 / 35
RGB: 106 / 75 / 68
HEX: 6A4B44

Orange
CMYK: 0 / 58 / 59 / 0
RGB: 255 / 135 / 102
HEX: #FF8766

Beige
CMYK: 4 / 11 / 15 / 0
RGB: 243 / 225 / 211
HEX: F3E1D3

Dark green
CMYK: 75 / 51 / 64 / 39
RGB: 56 / 79 / 72
HEX: #384F48

Green
CMYK: 70 / 0 / 47 / 0
RGB: 0 / 201 / 167
HEX: #00C9A7

Light green
CMYK: 19 / 0 / 12 / 0
RGB: 199 / 252 / 236
HEX: ##C7FCEC

Messages

Tagline and golden paragraph to describe the project

Tagline

PHA-based innovative agricultural solutions to deliver bio-based fertilizers and plant protection products

Short tagline

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

Golden paragraph

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams. Through demonstrations on horticultural crops and trees in Northern and Southern Europe, these proposed solutions, containing active bioproducts such as amino acids and microelements, have the potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

Typography

The typeface used for PHAntastic communications is Dita

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

PHA-based innovative agricultural solutions to deliver bio-based fertilizers and plant protection products

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams. Through demonstrations on horticultural crops and trees in Northern and Southern Europe, these proposed solutions, containing active bioproducts such as amino acids and microelements, have the potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

Dita Medium

Dita Bold

Dita Regular
Minimum font size for body text: 9pt

Typography

When the recommended typeface is not available, PHAntastic communications are to use the system font Calibri

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

PHA-based innovative agricultural solutions to deliver bio-based fertilizers and plant protection products

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams. Through demonstrations on horticultural crops and trees in Northern and Southern Europe, these proposed solutions, containing active bioproducts such as amino acids and microelements, have the potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

Calibri Bold

Calibri Regular
Minimum font size for body text: 9pt

Additional branding

Other logos and mentions to include in PHAntastic communications

As a Horizon Europe funded project, PHAntastic communication activities and products must also include the EU flag and following disclaimer:

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Contact

For any questions regarding these guidelines, please contact the communication partner:

Contact person

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